

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF INNOVATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7915984>

Abstract. *This article describes innovative processes and ways of accelerating them in the development of the economy of our country, and the role of innovations in the economy. When considering the main principles of management of innovation processes in economic systems, attention is paid to issues such as the specific characteristics of the innovation process, the general principles of organization management, and consideration of the characteristics of the participants of the innovation process.*

Keywords: *economic development, digital economy, innovation process management, innovation process, effective management system.*

Today, in the conditions of modernization of the economy, the most important condition for the successful management of our country, the main direction of socio-economic development, the development of high-tech and high-efficiency production, and the factor of competitiveness and growth of enterprises is the innovative feature.

In the last stages of the economic development of our country, great attention is paid to accelerating the innovation process. In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoev No. PF-6198 of 2021, it is noted as an important task that it is necessary to "Develop strategies for the development of priority sectors and industries based on scientific achievements and innovations based on long-term scenarios of innovative development of the country" [2], this topic confirms that it is one of the current issues.

In the conditions of the digital economy, it serves the development of enterprises, innovative renewal, modernization of production, introduction of new methods of company management, improvement of efficiency, assimilation of new types of products and services. Emphasis on innovation in enterprise activity, development and implementation of innovations, bringing them to the international level, increasing competitiveness, creating high added value and saving costs.

Many scientists have conducted scientific research on issues such as innovation management, innovative activities in enterprises, innovative processes, and during the preparation of this article, the works of a number of scientists were studied, including foreign scientists S.A. Agarkov, E.S. Kuznetsova, M.O. The Gryaznovas mainly studied innovative processes, innovative activities, organizational structures and a set of principles, methods and forms of management of employees involved in these activities [3]. Mamutov V.K. and those who highlighted the unique features of innovative activity in their work [10].

Local scientists D.N. Akobirova, I.J. Jakhongirov, M.A. Makhkamova, N. Makhmudov determined the nature of innovations in the development, modernization and diversification of the national economy, the role of investments in the economy of our country and ways of attracting them, and the development of innovative activities. conducted research. They mainly paid attention to issues of innovative development of industrial sectors in the course of structural changes. [4,5,6,7,8]

The methodological basis of the conducted research is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovative Activities", statutory and regulatory documents, as well as modern statistical methods and observations in the collection and processing of statistical data, as well as systematic analysis, historicity and rationality of scientific research, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative and selective research, monographic analysis and grouping methods were used.

Under the influence of a number of objective reasons, conditions and factors (the complexity of social needs, the rapid renewal of innovations, their knowledge intensity, etc.) in the conditions of market relations, regardless of the level of improvement of the national management system, an additional special mechanism of influence on the economy, social production, and the innovation process is needed.

Figure 1. An interconnected system of innovation process management

In social production, in the national economy, there are two interconnected systems of managing the innovation process, which were mentioned above.

The first system is a general system of social production management. In this case, the management of the innovation process is considered as a component of the management system of the national economy. This system is designed to solve all social production problems, and at the same time, to a certain extent, indirectly (indirectly) stimulates the development of the innovation process. It can also be called an exogenous (external) system of innovation process management.

The second system is the management system directly related to the innovation process itself. It can be called an endogenous (internal) management system of innovative processes.

The goals, content, tasks, principles and methods of the innovative process management system differ significantly from the management of other socio-economic processes. The goals of innovation process management are as follows:

- constantly updating the assortment and nomenclature of manufactured products, as well as the used equipment, technology, methods of production organization;
- further development of the country's scientific and scientific-technical potential, as well as creation of reserves.

Table 1.

The stage of the innovation process and its essence

Steps	The essence of the stage of the innovation process
Innovation is a new idea,	The results of completed scientific research (fundamental and applied), experimental project developments, other scientific and technical achievements. New ideas can be in the form of discoveries, rationalization proposals, concepts, methods, instructions, etc.

new knowledge	The result of introducing new knowledge, applying it to a new or improved product sold in the market or a new or improved technological process used in practice.
Innovation (implementation innovation)	The process of disseminating an innovation once mastered, i.e. applying innovative products, services, technologies in new places and conditions. The form and speed of implementation of this project depends on the structure and strength of communication channels, and the ability of business entities to quickly respond to innovations.

The essence of innovation process management (in a narrow sense) is to have a targeted impact on the process of research, project (design and technology) and innovation (innovation) development (economic, social, environmental) in order to reduce costs and deadlines and ultimately increase efficiency. In general, the essence of management can be revealed from the point of view of the exogenous system of management of the innovation process.

When considering the main principles of management of innovation processes in economic systems, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of the innovation process, the general principles of organization management, and the characteristics of the participants of the innovation process. Analysis of these features allows us to identify a number of key principles of innovation process management.

Management of the innovation process is carried out on the basis of general and specific principles of management based on the characteristics of the innovation and the content of the innovation. The latter is important for the formation of the innovation process management system itself, that is, for the creation of an endogenous management system. The specific principles of innovation process management include the principles of flexibility, taking into account the time factor, complexity, uncertainty of innovative works, their creative nature.

Figure 2. Specific principles of innovation process management

The above picture shows the specific principles of innovation process management, and one of the most important principles is the principle of flexibility. This is due to the nature of the process of scientific and technical development, and the results of scientific research are difficult to predict (even impossible to predict). The principle of flexibility requires the use of special types of planning (for example, not for specific detailed tasks, but for certain directions of research and

development) and forms of financing, which affects the composition of scientific and technical personnel and the choice of management methods.

Next is the principle of taking into account the time factor, in which the duration of the innovation process is related to the unevenness of the time interval for the implementation of its individual stages. The traditional calendar (quarter, year, etc.) cannot be used as a basis for managing the innovation process production cycles (except in rare cases). This principle is related to the perspective of innovation and implies the need to consider the long-term consequences of management decisions.

The principle of complexity implies technical, economic, organizational and information unity at all stages and all links of the innovation process. Such unity affects all components (elements) of the innovation management system: planning, financial and organizational support, etc. In addition, the principle of complexity means ensuring a close connection between different fields of science and management functions.

The principle of taking into account the uncertainty of innovative works and their risk is reflected in the methods of forecasting and planning, financing and evaluating the effectiveness of innovations. This requires, for example, the creation of financial reserves to eliminate (or reduce) the possible negative consequences of the risk, or to change the terms (phases) of the implementation of individual innovative works in the process of their planning.

The principle of taking into account the creative nature of innovative work or activity is based on the fact that the creative nature of creating and implementing innovations affects the management system of innovative processes. This is taken into account when organizing the work performance process, building the structure of management bodies, determining the work order and leadership style, evaluating the innovative work efficiency, especially encouraging the work of employees (materially and morally).

Management of the innovation process in accordance with the above and other principles is carried out on the basis of various methods. The methods of managing the innovation process are divided into administrative, organizational-planning, financial-economic and social-psychological methods. These methods are unique in their content, they differ from traditional methods used in production management, because innovative products (product innovation, technologies, methods) are a special type of product, distinguished by informational, organizational, moral and moral-psychological aspects of innovation and are important plays a role. It should be noted that the importance of financial and economic management methods increases significantly in the final stages of the innovation process. These methods cover many aspects of innovation process management.

Effective management of the innovation process is carried out through the innovation mechanism.

Innovation mechanism is organizational, management, financial, economic, legal, informational, technical and moral-psychological factors, their interdependence and interaction, which help to successfully implement innovative activities and increase the effectiveness of its results. According to this definition, the elements (components) of the innovation mechanism are:

- organizational forms of innovative relations;
- innovation management methods;
- innovation financing methods;
- methods of evaluating the effectiveness of innovative results;

- formation of innovative funds and their use (centralized and decentralized, regional, etc.);
- legislation regulating innovation processes;
- ethical and psychological methods of influencing innovative activity;
- measures of information and technical equipment of the innovation process.

The good functioning of the innovation mechanism, the joint activity of these elements is largely determined by their interdependence, correlation, and proportionality. The interdependence and structure of these elements, the importance and optimality of forms, methods and activities should correspond to the level of management at which the innovation policy is implemented.

Thus, the effective management of innovative processes is related to the integration of all elements of science and technology, production, and consumption systems in the course of enterprise activity, and in this regard, it is necessary to ensure the creation of a comprehensive system. Connecting the links in the innovation process - on the basis of feedback - also implies the stimulation of scientific research and the activation of inventive activity.

One of the main factors hindering the development of innovative activities in the enterprise is the lack of skills of employees. Despite the many benefits of innovation, such as cost reduction, reputation enhancement, customer loyalty, and many other positive aspects, not all companies develop or implement innovation. A radical revision of the company's policy is required for the widespread introduction or development of innovations. Innovative management in enterprises is unique, motivating all employees of the enterprise to improve the organizational structure based on constant mutual horizontal relations, to acquire new techniques and knowledge through continuous training, to achieve an increase in the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications, to ensure free thinking and initiative, to develop innovative, creative ideas. incentives include.

To create an effective management system in the enterprise, the following is necessary:

- providing flexible working conditions (schedule, workplace);
- creating and improving the collective spirit of the enterprise;
- creating conditions for rapid implementation of innovative ideas of employees (providing all resources, support from colleagues and management, etc.);
- elimination of bureaucratic obstacles or elements (continuous meetings, reports, etc.);
- proper placement of employees according to different positions and responsibilities;
- formation of a reliable environment ready for changes, support for freedom and creativity to create new ideas;
- development of a salary mechanism to encourage innovative, creative ideas of employees;
- not limiting the communication between management and ordinary employees and taking extra time to hear innovative ideas.

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